

A cloud-native approach for managing Kubernetes clusters in a hybrid cloud environment

September 2024

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Acknowledgement

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to **CERN Openlab** for providing invaluable opportunities to students from around the world, including those from non-member state countries. Their commitment to boosting students' careers with valuable internships is truly commendable.

I extend my heartfelt thanks to my supervisors, **Antonio** and **Arthur**, for their support, expert guidance, and patience throughout my internship. Their mentorship has been a huge plus to my learning and professional growth.

I am also grateful to my other teammates, **Hubert**, **Adrian**, and **Daniel**, who created a welcoming and supportive environment. Their kindness and willingness to assist made my internship experience both enjoyable and enriching.

Lastly, I want to acknowledge **my fellow summer students**, with a special mention to **Tomasz** and **Victor**, who were in the same team with me, and with whom I shared many memorable moments. The camaraderie we developed added a special dimension to this internship, creating friendships and connections that I will cherish long after this experience.

This summer at CERN has been an extraordinary journey of learning and personal growth. Hopefully, our paths will cross somewhere in the future.

~ Mouad ~

ABSTRACT

The Tomcat service has been operating in Kubernetes for the past four years. With the advent of new technologies, deployment methods have also evolved. In particular, some applications and components of the current infrastructure are already managed declaratively via Terraform and a GitOps controller. This project aims to explore how ClusterAPI and Crossplane can employ a declarative approach to manage and deploy Kubernetes clusters in a cloud-native way. Another important aspect of the project is interoperability; the proposed solution should be developed and tested both on-premise and on Oracle Cloud Infrastructure, further enhancing disaster recovery.

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1. Introduction

With the widespread and rapid adoption of Kubernetes as the framework for deploying applications, there has been a growing need for tools and services to manage Kubernetes clusters and deploy applications on them, especially at a large scale. Both on-premise and public cloud providers have had to adapt to this shift, offering both self-managed and managed services specifically tailored for provisioning and managing Kubernetes clusters.

Infrastructure as Code (IaC) tools also play a significant role in this new era by supporting these Kubernetes-specific services. Some IaC tools were designed from the ground up to be cloud-native, such as Crossplane, and run within Kubernetes, offering a unique approach to managing both infrastructure and applications. Others have focused specifically on the lifecycle management of Kubernetes clusters, such as ClusterAPI.

During my internship at CERN as an Openlab summer student, I had the privilege to work within the IT department in the team responsible for providing hosting infrastructure based on Kubernetes for **SSO** (Single Sign On) and many others critical java applications for Finance and Administrative Processes (FAP) and engineering (EN) departments such as **EDH** (Electronic Document Handling) and **EDMS** (Engineering & Equipment Data Management Service).

The team's Kubernetes clusters are all currently running within CERN on-premise OpenStack cloud and the current workflow for their management leverages Terraform as the IaC tool in addition to Gitlab CI/CD to automate cluster operations.

My project consisted of investigating how we can use Kubernetes-native IaC tools (ClusterAPI and Crossplane) in addition to GitOps practices (ArgoCD) for managing Kubernetes clusters on both on-premise CERN OpenStack cloud and Oracle public cloud (OCI) as a replacement to the current terraform and GitLab CI/CD approach. The aim of my supervisor was to have a unified way of managing both infrastructure and application through Kubernetes object. Another aspect is effective disaster recovery, with Kubernetes-native approach we can eliminate a lot of dependency present in the current approach and recover our clusters faster through a KinD or MiniKube cluster that can be run locally.

2. Existing workflows

a. Kubernetes clusters management

Our Kubernetes clusters are managed in CERN Openstack cloud through the **Magnum** [1] module which makes container orchestration engines (COE) such as Kubernetes available as first-class resources in OpenStack.

A cluster is created using a ClusterTemplate [2] which is a collection of parameters that describe how a cluster can be constructed. Some parameters are relevant to the infrastructure of the cluster, while others are for the particular COE.

Labels [3] are one of these parameters. They are a set of key/value pairs used for specifying additional parameters such as the packages that need to be installed on the cluster and their versions.

In CERN's OpenStack cloud, cluster templates are already defined and provided by the Kubernetes team. These templates include CERN-specific labels [4] in addition to those defined in Magnum's documentation. For each recent Kubernetes minor version, the Kubernetes team offers two types of templates:

- **single-AZ:** clusters created from this type of templates will have all their nodes located in one availability zone that user can define through a label.
- **multi-AZ:** used for creating a highly available cluster where nodes are spread across multiple availability zones.

In addition to multi-AZ templates, Nodegroups [5] are also used to enable high availability. Nodegroups are another first-class resource provided by the Magnum module. They represent a subset of nodes belonging to the same cluster that have similar properties and they can be assigned to a specific availability zone.

By default, when a cluster is created it already has two Nodegroups, '**default-master**' for master nodes and '**default-worker**' for worker nodes. In order to have a highly available cluster, user needs to explicitly create additional Nodegroups and spread them across multiple availability zone.

My team's approach consisted of using the templates provided by the Kubernetes team and overriding their labels with custom ones in order to provide Kubernetes environments that allow the execution of the applications we are responsible for.

Since there were multiple applications under my team's responsibilities, and for each of these applications there were test, dev, and prod clusters. Managing clusters manually through the OpenStack CLI was not an option, especially as these clusters were spread across multiple OpenStack projects. This is why the management system in place relied primarily on:

- **Terraform**, an IaC tool that allows cluster provisioning and management using a declarative configuration language (HCL - HashiCorp Configuration Language).
- **GitLab CI/CD pipeline**, which automates operations and reflect clusters specifications declared in the GitLab repository in the OpenStack cloud.

Figure 1. Current workflow for managing Kubernetes clusters lifecycle

As demonstrated in the figure above, the workflow functions as follows:

- when user pushes Terraform code describing a cluster specifications (see **Figure 10** in Appendix for an example) to the Git repository, the GitLab CI/CD pipeline will run on each push event and executes some Terraform commands (validate, plan, apply) triggering by that Terraform to send an API request to Openstack Magnum module which takes care of provisioning/upgrading the cluster.
- Once the clusters are created, the magnum module will respond with cluster's state which is then persisted by terraform in the backend (Postgres database) and the kubeconfig file of the cluster is saved in CERN secret store (Tbag/Teigi).

Despite the advantages of this approach, such as declarative cluster management and version control, there were two main drawbacks:

- Terraform is not Kubernetes-native and is not straightforward to maintain, as it uses HCL as a configuration language, while my team's work primarily involves Kubernetes objects/resources (YAML).
- It is not effective for disaster recovery, as there is a strong dependency on external CI/CD tools and a database.

b. Packages and Applications deployment on Kubernetes clusters

In addition to the infrastructure layer, the application layer management has its own workflow. Applications, along with additional packages like the monitoring stack, are managed using **ArgoCD** (a GitOps implementation), which automates deployment by continuously monitoring changes in Git repositories that host applications specifications (YAML code). ArgoCD ensures consistent and automated updates by synchronizing the desired applications state with Kubernetes clusters whenever changes are detected.

To further enhance maintainability, YAML code defining applications and packages is organized in a **Kustomize** [6] format. For each application, there is a base containing the common YAML code among all

the clusters and an overlay for each cluster that patches the base by adding, replacing, or removing code. The code ultimately deployed in each cluster is the result of applying the overlay patches to the base.

To connect the infrastructure and application layers, clusters created using the Terraform & GitLab CI/CD workflow must be registered as target clusters in the ArgoCD instance so that each application gets deployed to its designated cluster. Since both layers involve fundamentally different workflows, this process of registering target clusters is performed manually using the ArgoCD CLI tool.

3. Objectives

With the drawbacks of the current approach in mind, our main objective was to **propose a unified, cloud-native method for managing Kubernetes clusters** across both on-premises (OpenStack) and public cloud environments (Oracle Cloud Infrastructure). By **unified**, we mean using Kubernetes objects to manage applications and infrastructure on both on-premises and public cloud environments. By **cloud-native**, we mean that our IaC tool will run within Kubernetes and execute a reconciliation loop, constantly trying to align the current state of the clusters with their desired state specified in the Kubernetes resources.

Figure 2. A unified and cloud-native approach for managing Kubernetes clusters on hybrid cloud

Since GitOps (ArgoCD) has already been adopted for managing applications, we also wanted to **integrate the Kubernetes-native approach with the current ArgoCD workflow**. This way, when new clusters are created, they are automatically registered as target clusters within ArgoCD, making it easy for us to hydrate them with the required packages.

This setup will allow us to manage everything using Kubernetes and will eliminate many dependencies present in the current approach, leading to a more **effective disaster recovery** process that only requires:

- **A Kubernetes cluster:** which can be running on a local machine using KinD [7] or Minikube [8]

- **An ArgoCD instance:** running on that cluster

After that, all that is left is to point to the repository (which can be hosted locally, on GitLab, or GitHub) containing the YAML files necessary to deploy the IaC tool, the required providers, and the Kubernetes resources defining the clusters.

4. Investigations

a. Overview

To achieve the objectives outlined earlier, we conducted some investigations to explore the available cloud-native IaC tools and assess how they integrate with CERN Openstack and Oracle Cloud Infrastructure (OCI). We primarily focused on two tools that seemed to align with our use case:

- **ClusterAPI:** which is focused solely on the lifecycle management of Kubernetes clusters.
- **Crossplane:** a general-purpose IaC tool similar to Terraform but designed to run on Kubernetes. In fact, it is actually based on Terraform under the hood (providers are created using a code generation tool called **Upjet** [9] that allows code generation of Crossplane providers from Terraform providers).

The table below highlights the results of our investigations.

IaC tool / Cloud	OpenStack	Oracle Cloud Infrastructure
ClusterAPI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Does not support creating Kubernetes clusters through Magnum - It can be used as a backend for Magnum instead of Heat [10] service - Creating clusters using services other than Magnum does not work with CERN Openstack cloud due to networking constraints 	Supports creating both self-managed and managed clusters
Crossplane	Supports creating clusters through Magnum	No provider available (there is one , but it has been archived and it is not officially recognized by Crossplane)

b. CERN's OpenStack

i. ClusterAPI & Magnum

As described earlier, the lifecycle management of clusters on CERN's OpenStack cloud is handled through the Magnum module, where cluster templates are provided by the Kubernetes team. As a first step towards adopting ClusterAPI as a replacement for Terraform, we investigated whether ClusterAPI supports clusters lifecycle management through Magnum. It turned out that this was not the case. Instead, ClusterAPI uses other vanilla services, such as Nova (compute) and Neutron (networking), to create the infrastructure and bootstraps Kubernetes on top of that infrastructure using a specialized Kubernetes bootstrapping tool like Kubeadm [11] or MicroK8s [12].

During our investigation, we came across the **ClusterAPI driver for Magnum** [13]. Initially, we thought this would allow us to make ClusterAPI work with Magnum as a backend, but that was not the case. As a result of our in-depth investigations, we gained the following insights:

- Magnum uses another OpenStack module under the hood called Heat which is an orchestration service within OpenStack that automates the deployment and management of cloud resources using templates written in YAML or JSON. In simple terms, this module offers IaC as a service in OpenStack.
- Since Magnum was created before Kubernetes bootstrapping tools were available, it has its own way of bootstrapping Kubernetes clusters: an outdated method that lacks best practices adopted in specialized bootstrapping tools such as Kubeadm or MicroK8s.
- The Magnum codebase primarily consists of Bash scripts and Heat templates, making it difficult to maintain and explaining its slow support for newer Kubernetes versions.

The points mentioned above explain why some companies that relies heavily on Magnum developed the Magnum ClusterAPI driver, which is a patch that allows Magnum to use ClusterAPI as a backend instead of Heat. There are actually two ClusterAPI drivers built for Magnum available: one by VEXXHOST [14] and the other by StackHPC [15] (the latter is expected to be merged into OpenStack in Q4 2024).

ii. ClusterAPI & the vanilla approach: building the image

Since the vanilla approach was the only path through which we could potentially integrate ClusterAPI with CERN's OpenStack cloud, we wanted to explore that option further.

The first step with ClusterAPI, regardless of the cloud provider, is to generate an OS image compatible with the provider. This image is used to create the VMs that will serve as the cluster's nodes. It comes pre-bundled with Kubernetes components by default, simplifying cluster bootstrapping.

The process of image building for ClusterAPI is already automated, as they provide a dedicated tool called Image Builder [16]. All that is needed is to clone the repository, install some dependencies, and run the script that will generate the image based on the cloud provider.

Even though I followed all the steps mentioned in the [tutorial](#) for generating the image for OpenStack, the process failed in my case. After spending a lot of time debugging, it turned out that the issue was due to my LXPlus¹ machine running Red Hat. The script is designed to run only on Debian-based distributions, like Ubuntu, and will not work on other distributions.

To mitigate these Linux distributions issues, they provided an alternative called [remote image building](#). This approach allows you to give the building tool access to your OpenStack project, which will automatically provision an Ubuntu instance, run the script there, and upload the image to your OpenStack project. However, this also did not work because the remote image building process relies on floating IPs, which are not available in CERN OpenStack.

To successfully build the image, I ended up creating an Ubuntu VM myself, installing the tool and its dependencies on that VM, and running the script manually. Then, I wanted to copy that image from the VM to my LXPlus machine so that I could upload it to my OpenStack project, but this failed due to some disk limitations on LXPlus machines. As a workaround, I installed the OpenStack CLI on the Ubuntu VM itself, configured it with my OpenStack credentials, and was able to upload the image from there.

iii. ClusterAPI & the vanilla approach: installing ClusterAPI

After successfully building the image, the next step was to provision a management cluster, install ClusterAPI on that cluster, and configure it with my OpenStack project credentials. At first, I encountered a small issue where the installation was skipping cert-manager (one of the necessary dependencies for ClusterAPI to function properly), even though cert-manager was not installed on the cluster. This was causing the ClusterAPI installation to fail. It turned out that the cluster I was using, which was created from a template provided by the Kubernetes team, had only the CRDs (Custom Resource Definition) for cert-manager installed but not the CRs (Custom Resource) themselves. After manually deleting those CRDs and re-attempting the installation, everything worked fine.

iv. ClusterAPI & the vanilla approach: testing cluster creation

After setting up the management cluster, the next step was to attempt cluster creation on OpenStack using ClusterAPI. Before diving into the details of the tests we conducted, it is worth mentioning that ClusterAPI's

¹ **LXPLUS** is the interactive logon service to Linux for all CERN users. The cluster LXPLUS consists of public machines provided by the IT Department for interactive work.

key feature is its ability to roll out new machines for both worker nodes (managed by the MachineDeployment CR) and control plane nodes (managed by the KubeadmControlPlane CR) [17]. This feature is particularly useful for performing rolling upgrades of Kubernetes to newer versions and necessitates that the API server has a VIP (virtual IP) on the cluster network, enabling the underlying machine to be replaced without affecting the control plane endpoint. The OpenStack provider for ClusterAPI adheres to this constraint by offering users two options: using either a **floating IP** or a managed **load balancer**.

Besides using VIPs, the OpenStack provider will, by default, create a network, subnets, and a router connected to these subnets before creating the cluster VMs. All of these networking details are managed within the OpenStackCluster CR [18] , which will be the focus of the upcoming explanations.

Since provisioning a cluster from a specific availability zone is possible via Magnum and we rely heavily on this feature for managing our clusters, we wanted to investigate if this would be possible with ClusterAPI. Unfortunately, there is no option to specify the availability zone in the OpenStackCluster CR or in any other CRs. As a workaround, we explicitly defined the network and subnets in the OpenStackCluster CR where the cluster should be created. For the network, there is only one available in CERN OpenStack, called **CERN_NETWORK**. It has multiple subnets, from which we randomly selected one for our cluster, hoping that there is some form of binding between subnets and availability zones.

Regarding the VIP, since CERN OpenStack does not have floating IPs and offers only load balancers, we followed the latter option but faced several issues along the way that we highlighted in the table below.

Issue	Solution
CAPI OpenStack provider, by default, creates a port and attaches it to the load balancer. This operation failed in CERN OpenStack because ports, along with subnets and security groups, are abstracted and managed automatically. Users can only list these resources but cannot create, update, or delete them.	For ports specifically, it is possible to have creation rights by submitting a ticket to the OpenStack team and requesting network-admin privileges for your OpenStack project [19].
VM creation was taking so much time (20min) and then fails at the end with a message "failed to update DNS" and 500 error code.	Disabling the wait for DNS propagation by adding "cern-waitdns:false" key/value pair to the metadata of the VMs which can be specified through OpenStackMachineTemplate CR [20].
The created load balancer was not pingable.	Since I specified a random subnet for the cluster, it was also the subnet where the load balancer was created. My assumption was that load balancers

	<p>must be deployed in a specific set of subnets different from those dedicated to VMs, and the one I chose was not among them. To investigate that, I manually created a load balancer via the OpenStack dashboard to determine which subnet it would use, and then applied that same subnet to my cluster's load balancer while keeping the randomly selected subnet for the cluster VMs (see Figure 11 in Appendix)</p> <p>Theoretically, this workaround should have worked, but due to a bug in the CAPI OpenStack provider, it did not (see next issue for more details).</p>
<p>When you specify different subnets for the load balancer and the cluster's nodes, the subnet for the nodes is used to create both the load balancer and the nodes (this is a bug in the CAPI OpenStack provider).</p>	<p>I created a Github issue for this, and they said that they are going to work on it.</p>

After all this debugging and investigation, I wanted to confirm if my assumptions were valid and ensure that I had indeed reached a dead end with the bug I discovered in CAPI openstack provider. To do so, I asked the OpenStack team for some clarification, and they replied with the following:

- Loadbalancers created in CERN openstack are bound to a specific set of subnets. A loadbalancer is just a VM running haproxy and an agent inside that interacts with the APIs. This VM runs on one of our projects and has access to several subnets (dedicated just for the LBs). At this moment, we don't have the functionality to allow to use a subnet outside the dedicated ones.
- There is a naming convention for the subnets but there is no mapping between those and AZs at least not in MDC (Meyrin DataCenter). Subnets are connected to segments (or clusters in MDC) and those to hosts. The mapping of hosts and AZs is internal to the cloud service.
- MDC was never designed for AZs and the cloud service grew organically over the resources when they were available. This is why in the PDC (Prevessin DataCenter) we've started from scratch and things are clearer there.

The statements from the OpenStack team made it clear that we had reached a dead end on our side, leading to the conclusion that integrating ClusterAPI with CERN OpenStack is currently not feasible. However, this does not mean it is impossible. It may require a collaborative effort between multiple teams to explore

solutions like [kube-vip](#) and assess whether they can be leveraged in MDC, or possibly integrate ClusterAPI directly with PDC.

v. Crossplane

Unlike ClusterAPI, Crossplane supports creating Kubernetes clusters through Magnum because the code for the OpenStack provider, like many other providers in Crossplane, is generated from its equivalent Terraform provider using a code generation tool called Upjet. The **ClusterV1 CR** [21] is defined to represent the Cluster resource on OpenStack, while the **NodeGroupV1 CR** [22] is defined to represent Nodegroups (see [Figure 12](#) and [Figure 13](#) in Appendix for examples).

Since Terraform is being used under the hood, all the cluster lifecycle management operations performed via Terraform should be achievable through Crossplane. However, to be certain, we conducted some tests to ensure that Crossplane can replace Terraform in our cluster management workflow, particularly in the context of CERN's OpenStack. Test results and observations are highlighted in the table below.

Test	Result	Observation
creating a Cluster and a Nodegroup using a single-AZ clusterTemplate	success	the provider's API is still not very mature (some fields are duplicated, and others will be deprecated soon)
creating a highly available Cluster using a multi-AZ clusterTemplate	success	/
scaling master nodes (only possible for highly available clusters)	success	there is no feedback for updates, only for creation. To know whether the resource has been successfully updated, the user needs to manually compare the spec with the state (the update is successful when the state converges towards the spec)
creating a Nodegroup in a specific availability zone	success	/
scaling a Nodegroup up and down	success	no feedback for updates, only for creation.
deleting a Nodegroup	success	/
importing existing Clusters/Nodegroups	success	It works by adding "crossplane.io/external-name:<>" key/value pair to the annotations in the metadata of CR

updating Cluster labels in the Clusterv1 CR	a terraform error message is shown in the events of the Clusterv1 CR	there is no webhook that prevents updating immutable fields such as labels. Instead, a Terraform warning will be shown in the events of the CR
Reconciliation test: scaling a cluster created through Crossplane from the Openstack dashboard	Crossplane was not aware of this update (CR's state was not updated and no reconciliation action was triggered)	Crossplane has a weak reconciliation loop as it is based on Terraform under the hood

c. Oracle Cloud Infrastructure

i. ClusterAPI

Similarly to what we did with CERN OpenStack, the first step with OCI was to build the image that ClusterAPI would use to provision cluster VMs. However, the build process for OCI was slightly different. The Packer utility [23] used by the Image Builder tool creates a temporary VM in OCI, adds Kubernetes configurations to it, and then generates the image from that VM. The generated image is automatically uploaded to the cloud, and the temporary VM is cleaned up afterward. This explains why the build script requires OCI credentials to be passed as parameters, along with a subnet OCID where the temporary VM should be created [24].

After setting up a VCN using the 'Start VCN Wizard' utility [25], we created the required subnet and passed its OCID, along with the remaining parameters, to the script as described in the documentation. However, the build script was failing. It turned out that Packer was unable to connect to OCI because we were passing the credentials through the `'access_cfg_file'` field which references the config file of the OCI CLI. Overriding the authentication defaults resolved the issue, allowing the image to be built and uploaded successfully [26].

The next step was to test different cluster flavors provided by the CAPI OCI provider. For each flavor, there is a **template** YAML file that can be customized manually or by using the CAPI CLI tool (clusterctl). The tables below describe the tests we conducted for the flavor templates, as well as some additional tests.

Test 1	Creating a self-managed cluster (using <code>cluster-template.yaml</code>)
Results	Pods created using Deployments or ReplicaSets are pending, in contrast to pods created using DaemonSets
Details	Pods failed to get scheduled on nodes because of the following taint: <code>'node.cloudprovider.kubernetes.io/uninitialized=true'</code> .

	<p>This taint was still present and not removed from the nodes because the component responsible for this, OCI Cloud Controller Manager, was not installed on the cluster after its creation.</p> <p>CCMs [27] (Cloud Controller Managers) are very common when dealing with Kubernetes on public cloud. Since I mostly worked with Kubernetes in on-premise environments, I missed it.</p>
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Test 2	Creating a self-managed cluster with addons (using <u>cluster-template-oci-addons.yaml</u>)
Results	Success
Details	<p>This template could be really helpful for automating the deployment of CSI ², CNI ³, CCM, and any other required packages.</p> <p>This approach for creating clusters on OCI is the most suitable for CERN, as it is fundamentally similar to what is being used on-premises (cluster-template-oci-addons.yaml ↔ Magnum template, addons ↔ Magnum labels).</p>

Test 3	Creating a managed cluster from OKE (using <u>cluster-template-managed.yaml</u>)
Results	Nodepool was not created in OCI.
Details	<p>This template relies on the concept of machine pools, which is still an experimental feature in ClusterAPI. A feature flag must be enabled before installing CAPI providers (export EXP_MACHINE_POOL=true) and I missed that step.</p>

² **Container Storage Interface (CSI)**: CSI is a standardized interface that enables the integration of storage systems with Kubernetes.

³ **Container Network Interface (CNI)**: CNI provides a standardized way to manage the networking aspects of containerized applications, allowing different networking solutions (such as Calico, Flannel, or Weave) to integrate seamlessly.

Test 4	Using a kubeconfig file retrieved from ClusterAPI (clusterctl get kubconfig) for accessing managed clusters.
Results	The cluster was accessible for few minutes and then access was suddenly lost and the following error message was shown: you must be logged in to the server (Unauthorized).
Details	<p>The cluster's authentication token was changing every couple of minutes. The token in the kubeconfig I was using had expired, which explains the error message.</p> <p>OKE clusters have a special kubeconfig, retrieved only through the OCI CLI, that does not contain a static token for user authentication. Instead, it uses exec-based authentication, where every time a kubectl command is executed, a command from the OCI CLI is run to retrieve the token, which is then injected into the user request [28].</p> <p>clusterctl, in this case, was not retrieving the kubeconfig with exec-based authentication. It was only retrieving a kubeconfig with the current valid authentication token.</p> <p>The kubeconfig with exec-based authentication is only used for granting access to users who will interact with the cluster through kubectl. However, the kubeconfig generated by clusterctl is suitable for other purposes, such as CI/CD pipelines [28].</p> <p>A Clusterctl plugin could be implemented to support the retrieval of kubeconfig with exec-based authentication.</p>

Test 5	Creating a managed cluster with self-managed nodes (using <u>cluster-template-managed-self-managed-nodes.yaml</u>)
Results	worker machine is created and in running state in OCI but worker node never reaches a ready state in Kubernetes although all <u>the requirements</u> are fulfilled.
Details	/

Test 6	Testing reconciliation by scaling a managed cluster from the OCI UI.
Results	<p>The state changed in the CRs but the controller didn't try to take down new node.</p> <p>The status of the cluster in the OCI UI was alternating between 'updating' and 'active' all the time.</p>
Details	<p>When scaling up, the 'status.phase' of the MachinePool CR is set to 'scaling', 'status.NodepoolLifecycleState' is set to 'updating' in OCIManagedMachinePool CR (see Figure 15 and Figure 16 in Appendix).</p> <p>When scaling down, MachinePool CR went back to its normal state ('status.phase' set to 'running') but "status.NodepoolLifecycleState" OCIManagedMachinePool CR was still set to UPDATING and the cluster state in the OCI UI was still constantly switching between "running" and "updating".</p>

ii. Crossplane

During my search through the Upbound marketplace for Crossplane providers [29], I noticed that the OCI provider was notably absent from the extensive collection of over 100 providers, which included all major public cloud vendors. Upon further investigation, I found a blog post from Oracle [30] offering a pre-release preview of a Crossplane provider, but it didn't link to any code source. Later on in my search, I stumbled across a project for the provider on GitHub [31] where development efforts had begun but were discontinued 6 months later, leading to the repository being recently archived.

Having an OCI Crossplane provider would be very beneficial for people who use OKE and want to manage everything from Kubernetes. Hybrid cloud is another scenario where the provider would be helpful, and the CERN use case is a perfect example of that. In addition to these compelling use cases, Upjet can significantly reduce the development effort and time required for the Crossplane provider, as it can be leveraged to generate boilerplate code from the existing Terraform provider.

5. Proposed Approach

Our investigation results indicated that neither ClusterAPI nor Crossplane is capable of provisioning Kubernetes clusters on both CERN OpenStack and Oracle Cloud Infrastructure. Each tool's compatibility is mutually exclusive (if one tool supports a particular provider, it lacks support for the other).

Despite Crossplane not being the optimal solution due to its lack of strong reconciliation, we opted for it anyway because all Kubernetes clusters under my team's responsibility are currently running in CERN OpenStack, and we don't have any clusters running on Oracle yet. In addition to Crossplane, ArgoCD is also leveraged as a Kubernetes-native CD pipeline to automate clusters lifecycle management following the GitOps approach.

ArgoCD and Crossplane are deployed in the **management cluster**, which can be hosted on any cloud provider or even locally using KinD or Minikube. The **management cluster** is responsible only for executing cluster operations and hosting clusters specifications as Kubernetes objects, contrary to **workload clusters** where applications will be actually running.

Figure 3. Newly proposed workflow for managing Kubernetes clusters lifecycle

The workflow, as described in the figure above, functions as follows:

- The user will push YAML code defining cluster specifications to a Git repository that can be hosted on GitLab, GitHub, or even locally.
- ArgoCD, running in the management cluster, will constantly watch for newly added cluster specifications in the Git repository and deploy them as Crossplane custom resources (Kubernetes Objects) within the management cluster.
- The reconciliation loop executed by the Crossplane controllers will detect these newly added custom resources and trigger the creation of a workload cluster on the CERN OpenStack cloud.

6. The one button deployment

In the previous section, we explained how our approach works, its internal architecture, and how the components within this architecture communicate with each other to achieve the intended functionalities. Now, we will dive deeper into the details and explain our automated approach for setting up the management cluster with all the necessary components, as well as how to configure them to collaborate effectively.

Before discussing automation, let me first walk you through the scenario we would need to follow if we wanted to do everything manually. The table below outlines each step of this scenario and explains some of its details.

Step N°	Actions	Explanation
0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provision a Kubernetes cluster Install ArgoCD on that cluster 	The Kubernetes cluster will serve as the management cluster and will host ArgoCD, Crossplane and the custom resources that will describe our clusters.
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Install Crossplane core [32] 	Crossplane has a plugin architecture where there is the core component and a plugin for each cloud often called providers.
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Install openstack-provider [33] for Crossplane Install argocd-provider [34] for Crossplane 	<p>The openstack-provider will allow us to create or manage already existing cluster on the CERN OpenStack cloud.</p> <p>The argocd-provider is used for automating the registrations of these clusters in ArgoCD as target clusters for application deployments.</p>
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Install openstack-provider-config [35] Install argocd-provider-config [36] 	In this step, we will configure the openstack-provider with our OpenStack cloud credentials and the argocd-provider with the credentials of an ArgoCD admin user needed for registering clusters created/imported using Crossplane as target clusters within ArgoCD.
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deploy Crossplane custom resource that will represent our clusters 	This will include custom resources for both <i>openstack-provider</i> (Clusterv1, Nodegroupv1) and <i>argocd-provider</i> (Cluster) (see Figure 12 , Figure 13 and Figure 14 for in Appendix for examples)
5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Deploy packages/applications 	This step is optional but can be executed to hydrate newly created clusters with the packages/dependencies needed by applications or deploy applications themselves directly.

To automate this process as much as possible, we leveraged the **app of apps pattern** [37] in addition to the **sync waves feature** [38] of ArgoCD, where each step (from 1 to 5) is represented through an ArgoCD

application with the step number set as its sync wave value (see [Figure 18](#), [Figure 19](#) and [Figure 20](#) in Appendix for examples). It is important to note, however, that using sync waves with Crossplane custom resources does not work by default and requires additional configuration to function properly [39].

The main app, in the app-of-apps architecture, will be responsible for deploying the five applications that represent the five steps, ensuring that the logical order of deployment is respected: applications with higher sync wave values will not be deployed until those with lower sync wave values are deployed and in a healthy state (see [Figure 17](#) in Appendix).

As a result, deploying the main app (which can happen with a one-button click) will lead to the setup of the management cluster, the provisioning/import of OpenStack clusters, and deployment of packages/applications on top of these clusters. This one-button deployment is particularly useful for disaster recovery, as it automates the entire process from end to end, without relying on any external dependencies that could also be affected by the disaster.

7. Migration

a. Translating Terraform to Crossplane

Now that we have validated our new cluster management approach and the one-button deployment method, the final step will be to translate our cluster specifications written in HCL into Crossplane custom resources, which will be deployed through ArgoCD in the management cluster.

Since we already use Kustomize in conjunction with ArgoCD for deploying applications and packages, we decided to do the same with clusters. Another reason behind this decision is to allow for easy maintenance of cluster artifacts, as they share many common fields, especially between ones created from the same template. With Kustomize, we will have a base for each cluster template and an overlay for each cluster created from that template, which will customize the base by updating and adding new properties to match the specifications defined in Terraform.

However, since cluster specifications and OpenStack credentials are managed separately in Crossplane (each defined in a separate CR), unlike in Terraform, where everything is included in the tfvars file, we decided to maintain a dedicated base for OpenStack configurations (see [Figure 21](#) and [Figure 22](#) in Appendix) and multiple overlays for each OpenStack project, patching the base with the project's credentials.

To automate the translation process, we wrote a Python script that parses cluster specifications written in HCL (tfvars file) and generates both config and cluster overlays. The base, on the other hand, is created manually in both cases.

Creating the base for the config was relatively straightforward compared to the cluster one, where we needed to identify the fields that are common in all clusters created from the same template. One emerging challenge here was labels. The labels are almost identical between clusters created using the same template, with one to a maximum of three labels changing from one cluster to another.

By performing 'diff' operations between clusters created using the same template, we identified the lowest common denominator of labels corresponding to a cluster template and included these labels in its base (see [Figure 23](#) and [Figure 24](#) in Appendix for an example). For the remaining labels, we identified two categories:

- **Optional labels:** These are not present in all cluster specifications, so they are not included in the base but might be added in overlays as a patch to the base using an “add” operation.
- **Changing labels:** These labels have a common value across most clusters, except for a small subset where the value differs. They are included in the base with their common value and might be patched in the overlay using a “replace” operation if the value differs from the common one.

Optional and changing labels are defined for each cluster template and represented using a Python dictionary as showcased in the figure below. This dictionary is leveraged by the translation algorithm for generating cluster overlays.

```

TEMPLATES = {
  "v1.29":{
    "v1.29.2-1":{
      "optional_labels": ["availability_zone"],
      "changing_labels": {
        "cephfs_csi_enabled": "false",
        "manila_csi_enabled": "false",
        "manila_enabled": "false"
      }
    },
    "v1.29.2-1-multi":{
      "optional_labels": [],
      "changing_labels": {
        "cephfs_csi_enabled": "false",
        "manila_csi_enabled": "false",
        "manila_enabled": "false"
      }
    }
  }
}

```



```

    }
  },
  "v1.29.2-2-multi":{
    "optional_labels": [],
    "changing_labels": {}
  }
}
}
}

```

Figure 4. Excerpt from the changing and optional labels python dictionary

Both cluster and config overlays consist of a set of YAML files. To simplify the generation of these files, we created a template for each overlay file using Jinja [40] as the templating engine (see [Figure 25](#) in Appendix for an example). The translation algorithm, as shown in the figure below, loads and customizes these templates based on the parsed cluster specifications and the identified changing/optional labels (the parsed cluster specifications are passed as a parameter in both `render_config_overlay()` and `render_cluster_overlay()` function calls. However, only the `render_cluster_overlay()` function requires the changing/optional labels and utilizes the **TEMPLATES** dictionary, which is declared as a global variable).

```

in_dir = sys.argv[1]
out_dir = sys.argv[2]

# loop over communities
for community_dir in os.listdir(in_dir):
    # get input and output paths for communities
    in_community_dir_path = os.path.join(in_dir, community_dir)
    out_community_dir_path = os.path.join(out_dir, community_dir)

    # create output community
    os.makedirs(out_community_dir_path, exist_ok=True)

    # create config under output community
    config_path = os.path.join(out_community_dir_path, "config")
    os.makedirs(config_path, exist_ok=True)

    # copy config overlay kustomization.yaml
    shutil.copy2(
        "./overlay-templates/config/kustomization.yaml",
        os.path.join(config_path, "kustomization.yaml")
    )
    first_dir = 0
    # loop over clusters
    for cluster_dir in os.listdir(in_community_dir_path):

```



```

# get input and output path for clusters
in_cluster_dir_path = os.path.join(in_community_dir_path, cluster_dir)
out_cluster_dir_path = os.path.join(out_community_dir_path, cluster_dir)

# create output cluster
os.makedirs(out_cluster_dir_path, exist_ok=True)

# render overlays
with open(os.path.join(in_cluster_dir_path, "terraform.tfvars"), 'r') as file:
    # translate tfvars file to python dict
    tfvars_dict = hcl2.load(file)

# render config overlay
if first_dir == 0:
    first_dir = 1
    patch_provider_config, patch_secret = render_config_overlay(tfvars_dict)
    with open(os.path.join(config_path, 'patch-provider-config.yaml'), 'w') as file:
        file.write(patch_provider_config)
    with open(os.path.join(config_path, 'patch-secret.yaml'), 'w') as file:
        file.write(patch_secret)

# render cluster overlay
kustomization, patch_cluster, patch_clusterv1, nodegroupv1 = render_cluster_overlay(tfvars_dict)
with open(os.path.join(out_cluster_dir_path, 'kustomization.yaml'), 'w') as file:
    file.write(kustomization)
with open(os.path.join(out_cluster_dir_path, 'patch-cluster.yaml'), 'w') as file:
    file.write(patch_cluster)
with open(os.path.join(out_cluster_dir_path, 'patch-clusterv1.yaml'), 'w') as file:
    file.write(patch_clusterv1)
if nodegroupv1:
    with open(os.path.join(out_cluster_dir_path, 'nodegroupv1.yaml'), 'w') as file:
        file.write(nodegroupv1)

```

Figure 5. Terraform to Crossplane translation script

b. Secret management

As we mentioned earlier, saving the kubeconfig files for newly created clusters was the final step in the Terraform & GitLab CI/CD workflow. To ensure that the entire workflow is migrated to ArgoCD & Crossplane, we had to implement a new approach for secret management.

When clusters are created through Crossplane openstack provider, their kubeconfig is saved in a Secret resource of type '**connection.crossplane.io/v1alpha1**', specifically as a value to the '**attribute.kubeconfig.raw_config**' key. Based on this default Crossplane behavior for kubeconfig

management, we created a CronJob that will be deployed on the management cluster and will constantly monitor for newly created kubeconfig secrets, retrieve the value of the kubeconfig key, decode it, and save it in CERN's secret store using its dedicated CLI.

The figures below demonstrate the cronjob code and the YAML artifacts used for its deployment on Kubernetes.

```

from kubernetes import client, config
import base64
import os

def main():
    namespace = os.environ.get('NAMESPACE', 'crossplane-clusters')
    secret_type = os.environ.get('SECRET_TYPE', 'connection.crossplane.io/v1alpha1')
    kubeconfig_key = os.environ.get('KUBECONFIG_KEY', 'attribute.kubeconfig.raw_config')

    config.load_incluster_config()
    v1 = client.CoreV1Api()

    secrets = v1.list_namespaced_secret(namespace)

    filtered_secrets = [
        secret for secret in secrets.items
        if secret.type == secret_type
    ]

    for s in filtered_secrets:
        kubeconfig_encoded = s.data.get(kubeconfig_key)
        kubeconfig_decoded = base64.b64decode(kubeconfig_encoded).decode('utf-8')
        print(kubeconfig_decoded)
        # save kubeconfig in the secret store
        # ...

if __name__ == '__main__':
    main()

```

Figure 6. *python code for the kubeconfig cronjob*

```

FROM python:3.9-slim

WORKDIR /app

```



```

COPY main.py .

COPY requirements.txt .

RUN pip install --no-cache-dir -r requirements.txt

CMD ["python3", "main.py"]

```

Figure 7. Dockerfile for containerizing the python code

```

apiVersion: v1
kind: ServiceAccount
metadata:
  name: kubeconfig-logger
  namespace: default
imagePullSecrets:
- name: regcred
---
kind: ClusterRole
apiVersion: rbac.authorization.k8s.io/v1
metadata:
  name: kubeconfig-logger
rules:
- apiGroups: [""]
  resources: ["secrets"]
  verbs: ["get", "watch", "list"]
---
kind: ClusterRoleBinding
apiVersion: rbac.authorization.k8s.io/v1
metadata:
  name: kubeconfig-logger
subjects:
- kind: ServiceAccount
  name: kubeconfig-logger
  namespace: default
roleRef:
  kind: ClusterRole
  name: kubeconfig-logger
  apiGroup: rbac.authorization.k8s.io

```

Figure 8. RBAC resources definition

```

apiVersion: batch/v1
kind: CronJob

```



```

metadata:
  name: kubeconfig-logger
  namespace: default
spec:
  schedule: "*/1 * * * *"
  jobTemplate:
    spec:
      template:
        spec:
          serviceAccountName: kubeconfig-logger
          containers:
            - name: kubeconfig-logger
              image: <registry_url>/kubeconfig-logger
              env:
                - name: NAMESPACE
                  value: crossplane-clusters
                - name: SECRET_TYPE
                  value: connection.crossplane.io/v1alpha1
                - name: KUBECONFIG_KEY
                  value: attribute.kubeconfig.raw_config
          restartPolicy: Never

```

Figure 9. Cronjob resource definition

8. Conclusion & Perspectives

Through our exploration of cloud-native IaC tools and their integration with CERN OpenStack and Oracle Cloud Infrastructure, we encountered several obstacles that currently prevent hybrid cloud support:

- ClusterAPI lacking the capability of creating Kubernetes clusters through OpenStack Magnum module
- CERN OpenStack networking constraint preventing ClusterAPI from creating Kubernetes clusters in a vanilla way using other services (Nova, Neutron ...etc)
- the absence of Crossplane provider for Oracle Cloud Infrastructure

Since all our clusters runs currently on OpenStack, the Crossplane choice was inevitable despite not being the optimal solution (weak reconciliation & uses terraform under the hood). However, using Crossplane had its advantages too as it offered many utilities that made the full migration from terraform possible:

- the possibility to import existing clusters
- the presence of an *argocd-provider* allowing automatic registration of newly created clusters as targets in ArgoCD instead of the manual approach used for clusters created through terraform

Furthermore, by exploring ArgoCD in depth and leveraging its app-of-apps pattern in addition to its sync waves functionality, we were able to both automate the migration process and establish a one-button disaster recovery mechanism, enabling effective and easy recovery of our workload clusters through a simple Minikube/KinD management cluster that can be spawned locally.

One key aspect of migration was translating clusters specifications written in HCL into custom resources that the openstack-provider from Crossplane can understand. Instead of relying on manual translation which can be error-prone especially in the medium scale we were operating in (more than 40 clusters including dev, test and prod clusters), we went for an automated approach by writing a python script that walks through all cluster specifications written in HCL and translate them into custom resources. Since clusters created from the same template shared many common properties, and to make the YAML code more maintainable, we organized our cluster artifacts using the Kustomize format.

For the future, our work could provide a solid foundation for enabling a multi-cloud environment by addressing the gaps in either Crossplane or ClusterAPI. As for crossplane, we can leverage the Openlab-Oracle partnership to provide feedback on the missing OCI provider and collaborate more with them regarding this matter. For ClusterAPI, integrating with CERN OpenStack cloud is not impossible. It can be done but this will require a collaborative effort between multiple teams and the chances of success are higher with the new Preveessin datacentre that does not have the networking constraints present in the Meyrin one.

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10. Appendix

```
# Openrc parameters
auth_url          = "<auth_url>"
identity_api_version = "<identity_api_version>"
interface         = "<interface>"
keypair           = "<keypair>"
project_id        = "<project_id>"
project_name      = "JEEDY AIS"
region_name       = "cern"

# Cluster parameters
cluster_name      = "k8s-ais-batch-dev-multi-v25"
cluster_template_name = "kubernetes-1.25.3-3-multi"
create_timeout    = "60"
flavor            = "m2.xlarge"
master_count      = "1"
master_flavor     = "m2.xlarge"
node_count        = "1"

# Nodegroups definition
nodegroups_list = [
  {
    flavor_id      = "m2.xlarge",
    merge_labels   = "true",
    name           = "zone-a-xlarge",
    node_count     = "1",
    labels = {
      availability_zone = "cern-geneva-a"
    }
  },
  {
    flavor_id      = "m2.xlarge",
    merge_labels   = "true",
    name           = "zone-b-xlarge",
    node_count     = "2",
    labels = {
      availability_zone = "cern-geneva-b"
    }
  },
  {
    flavor_id      = "m2.xlarge",
    merge_labels   = "true",
    name           = "zone-c-xlarge",
    node_count     = "2",
    labels = {
```



```

        availability_zone = "cern-geneva-c"
    }
}
]
# Labels for kubernetes cluster
labels = {
    "admission_control_list" :
"ExtendedResourceToleration,NamespaceLifecycle,LimitRanger,ServiceAccount,DefaultStorageClass,DefaultTolerationSeconds,MutatingAdmissionWebhook,ValidatingAdmissionWebhook,ResourceQuota,Priority",
    "autoscaler_tag" : "v1.21.0-cern.0",
    "calico_ipv4pool" : "10.100.0.0/16",
    "calico_ipv4pool_ipip" : "Always",
    "calico_tag" : "v3.24.5",
    "cephfs_csi_enabled" : "false",
    "cephfs_csi_version" : "cern-csi-1.0-3",
    "cern_chart_enabled" : "true",
    "cern_chart_version" : "0.12.0",
    "cert_manager_api" : "true",
    "cgroup_driver" : "cgroupfs",
    "cloud_provider_enabled" : "true",
    "cloud_provider_tag" : "v1.24.5",
    "container_infra_prefix" : "<container_infra_prefix>",
    "container_runtime" : "containerd",
    "containerd_tarball_sha256" : "<containerd_tarball_sha256>",
    "containerd_tarball_url" : "<containerd_tarball_url>",
    "coredns_tag" : "1.8.7",
    "cvmfs_csi_enabled" : "false",
    "cvmfs_csi_version" : "v2.0.0",
    "eos_enabled" : "false",
    "etcd_tag" : "v3.4.13",
    "heapster_enabled" : "false",
    "heat_container_agent_tag" : "train-stable-6",
    "helm_client_tag" : "v2.16.6",
    "ignition_version" : "3.3.0",
    "influx_grafana_dashboard_enabled" : "false",
    "ingress_controller" : "",
    "ip_family_policy" : "single_stack",
    "keystone_auth_enabled" : "true",
    "kube_csi_enabled" : "false",
    "kube_csi_version" : "cern-csi-1.0-2",
    "kube_dashboard_enabled" : "false",
    "kube_tag" : "v1.25.3-cern.0",
    "kubepi_options" : "--feature-gates=CSIMigration=true",

```



```

"kubecontroller_options" : "--feature-gates=",
"kubelet_options" : "--feature-gates= --system-reserved=memory=500Mi --
resolv-conf=/run/systemd/resolve/resolv.conf",
"logging_installer" : "helm",
"manila_csi_enabled" : "false",
"manila_enabled" : "false",
"manila_version" : "v0.3.0",
"metrics_server_enabled" : "true",
"monitoring_enabled" : "false",
"nginx_ingress_controller_tag" : "v1.0.4",
"nvidia_gpu_enabled" : "false",
"nvidia_gpu_tag" : "35-5.16.13-200.fc35.x86_64-470.82.00",
"oidc_enabled" : "false",
"oidc_groups_claim" : "<oidc_groups_claim>",
"oidc_groups_prefix" : "<oidc_groups_prefix>",
"oidc_issuer_url" : "<oidc_issuer_url>",
"oidc_username_claim" : "<oidc_username_claim>",
"oidc_username_prefix" : "<oidc_username_prefix>",
"snapshot_controller_enabled" : "false",
"tiller_enabled" : "true",
"tiller_tag" : "v2.16.6",
"traefik_ingress_controller_tag" : "2.5.4",
"use_podman" : "true"
}

```

Figure 10. Tfvars file example

```

apiVersion: infrastructure.cluster.x-k8s.io/v1beta1
kind: OpenStackCluster
metadata:
  name: capi-test
  namespace: default
spec:
  apiServerLoadBalancer:
    enabled: true
    network:
      id: <network_id>
    subnets:
      - id: <subnet_1_id>
  identityRef:
    cloudName: openstack
    name: capi-test-cloud-config
  network:
    id: <network_id>

```



```
subnets:
  - id: <subnet_2_id>
disableExternalNetwork: true
disableAPIServerFloatingIP: true
```

Figure 11. OpenstackCluster CR used for testing CAPI with CERN openstack

```
apiVersion: containerinfra.openstack.crossplane.io/v1alpha1
kind: ClusterV1
metadata:
  annotations:
    crossplane.io/external-name: k8s-ais-batch-dev-multi-v25
  name: k8s-ais-batch-dev-multi-v25
spec:
  deletionPolicy: Orphan
  forProvider:
    clusterTemplateId: kubernetes-1.25.3-3-multi
    createTimeout: 60
    flavor: m2.xlarge
    keypair: shared-jeedy-key
    labels:
      admission_control_list:
        ExtendedResourceToleration, NamespaceLifecycle, LimitRanger, ServiceAccount, DefaultStorageClass, DefaultTolerationSeconds, MutatingAdmissionWebhook, ValidatingAdmissionWebhook, ResourceQuota, Priority
      autoscaler_tag: v1.21.0-cern.0
      calico_ipv4pool: 10.100.0.0/16
      calico_ipv4pool_ipip: Always
      calico_tag: v3.24.5
      cephfs_csi_enabled: "false"
      cephfs_csi_version: cern-csi-1.0-3
      cern_chart_enabled: "true"
      cern_chart_version: 0.12.0
      cert_manager_api: "true"
      cgroup_driver: cgroupfs
      cloud_provider_enabled: "true"
      cloud_provider_tag: v1.24.5
      container_infra_prefix: <container_infra_prefix>
      container_runtime: containerd
      containerd_tarball_sha256: <containerd_tarball_sha256>
      containerd_tarball_url: <containerd_tarball_url>
      coredns_tag: 1.8.7
      cvmfs_csi_enabled: "false"
      cvmfs_csi_version: v2.0.0
```



```
eos_enabled: "false"
etcd_tag: v3.4.13
heapster_enabled: "false"
heat_container_agent_tag: train-stable-6
helm_client_tag: v2.16.6
ignition_version: 3.3.0
influx_grafana_dashboard_enabled: "false"
ingress_controller: ""
ip_family_policy: single_stack
keystone_auth_enabled: "true"
kube_csi_enabled: "false"
kube_csi_version: cern-csi-1.0-2
kube_dashboard_enabled: "false"
kube_tag: v1.25.3-cern.0
kubeapi_options: --feature-gates=CSIMigration=true
kubecntroller_options: --feature-gates=
kubelet_options: --feature-gates= --system-reserved=memory=500Mi --
resolv-conf=/run/systemd/resolve/resolv.conf
logging_installer: helm
manila_csi_enabled: "false"
manila_enabled: "false"
manila_version: v0.3.0
metrics_server_enabled: "true"
monitoring_enabled: "false"
nginx_ingress_controller_tag: v1.0.4
nvidia_gpu_enabled: "false"
nvidia_gpu_tag: 35-5.16.13-200.fc35.x86_64-470.82.00
oidc_enabled: "false"
oidc_groups_claim: <oidc_groups_claim>
oidc_groups_prefix: <oidc_groups_prefix>
oidc_issuer_url: <oidc_issuer_url>
oidc_username_claim: <oidc_username_claim>
oidc_username_prefix: <oidc_username_prefix>
snapshot_controller_enabled: "false"
tiller_enabled: "true"
tiller_tag: v2.16.6
traefik_ingress_controller_tag: 2.5.4
use_podman: "true"
masterCount: 1
masterFlavor: m2.xlarge
mergeLabels: true
name: k8s-ais-batch-dev-multi-v25
nodeCount: 1
providerConfigRef:
```



```

name: jeedy-ais
writeConnectionSecretToRef:
  name: k8s-ais-batch-dev-multi-v25
  namespace: crossplane-clusters

```

Figure 12. Clusterv1 CR example (crossplane-openstack-provider)

```

apiVersion: containerinfra.openstack.crossplane.io/v1alpha1
kind: NodegroupV1
metadata:
  annotations:
    crossplane.io/external-name: k8s-ais-batch-dev-multi-v25/zone-a-xlarge
  name: zone-a-xlarge
spec:
  deletionPolicy: Orphan
  forProvider:
    clusterId: k8s-ais-batch-dev-multi-v25
    flavorId: m2.xlarge
    labels:
      availability_zone: cern-geneva-a
    mergeLabels: true
    name: zone-a-xlarge
    nodeCount: 1
  providerConfigRef:
    name: jeedy-ais

```

Figure 13. Nodegroupv1 CR example (crossplane-openstack-provider)

```

apiVersion: cluster.argocd.crossplane.io/v1alpha1
kind: Cluster
metadata:
  name: k8s-ais-batch-dev-multi-v25
spec:
  forProvider:
    config:
      kubeconfigSecretRef:
        key: attribute.kubeconfig.raw_config
        name: k8s-ais-batch-dev-multi-v25
        namespace: crossplane-clusters
      name: k8s-ais-batch-dev-multi-v25
  providerConfigRef:
    name: argocd-provider

```

Figure 14. Cluster CR example (crossplane-argocd-provider)


```
Name:          oci-capi-managed-mp-0
Namespace:     default
Labels:        cluster.x-k8s.io/cluster-name=oci-capi-managed
Annotations:   cluster.x-k8s.io/replicas-managed-by:
API Version:   cluster.x-k8s.io/v1beta1
Kind:          MachinePool
Metadata:
  Creation Timestamp:  2024-08-13T09:21:07Z
  Finalizers:
    machinepool.cluster.x-k8s.io
  Generation:         4
  Owner References:
    API Version:      cluster.x-k8s.io/v1beta1
    Kind:              Cluster
    Name:              oci-capi-managed
    UID:               d858ab51-27df-42a0-9a80-51f0c1c90f62
  Resource Version:   7108296
  UID:                32801290-c721-4e89-a18a-5594e705f574
Spec:
  Cluster Name:       oci-capi-managed
  Min Ready Seconds:  0
  Provider ID List:
    <ocid1.instance.oc1.eu-frankfurt-1...>
    <ocid1.instance.oc1.eu-frankfurt-1...>
  Replicas:          1
  Template:
    Metadata:
      Spec:
        Bootstrap:
          Data Secret Name:
        Cluster Name:       oci-capi-managed
        Infrastructure Ref:
          API Version:   infrastructure.cluster.x-k8s.io/v1beta1
          Kind:          OCIManagedMachinePool
          Name:          oci-capi-managed-mp-0
          Namespace:     default
          Version:       v1.30.1
    Status:
      Available Replicas:  2
      Bootstrap Ready:    true
      Conditions:
        Last Transition Time:  2024-08-13T09:41:18Z
        Status:                True
        Type:                   Ready
```



```

Last Transition Time: 2024-08-13T09:21:07Z
Status:              True
Type:                BootstrapReady
Last Transition Time: 2024-08-13T09:32:38Z
Status:              True
Type:                InfrastructureReady
Last Transition Time: 2024-08-13T09:41:18Z
Status:              True
Type:                ReplicasReady
Infrastructure Ready: true
Node Refs:
  API Version:       v1
  Kind:              Node
  Name:              10.0.78.220
  UID:              df0b8645-ee4d-4b2a-9413-48b8ea7fa038
  API Version:       v1
  Kind:              Node
  Name:              10.0.69.111
  UID:              75df6b54-76e9-4da0-8e8b-40edc0e5ad51
Observed Generation: 4
Phase:               Scaling
Ready Replicas:      2
Replicas:             2
Unavailable Replicas: -1
Events:              <none>

```

Figure 15. MachinePool CR after reconciliation test of CAPI on OCI

```

Name:                oci-capi-managed-mp-0
Namespace:           default
Labels:              cluster.x-k8s.io/cluster-name=oci-capi-managed
Annotations:         <none>
API Version:         infrastructure.cluster.x-k8s.io/v1beta2
Kind:                OCIManagedMachinePool
Metadata:
  Creation Timestamp: 2024-08-13T09:21:07Z
  Finalizers:
    ocimanagedmachinepool.infrastructure.cluster.x-k8s.io
  Generation:        4
  Owner References:
    API Version:      cluster.x-k8s.io/v1beta1
    Block Owner Deletion: true
    Controller:       true
    Kind:             MachinePool

```



```
Name:                oci-capi-managed-mp-0
UID:                 32801290-c721-4e89-a18a-5594e705f574
Resource Version:   7553555
UID:                 13c6eaca-28de-4756-b70e-6eb76e19b896
Spec:
  Id: <ocid1.nodepool.oc1.eu-frankfurt-1...>
  Node Pool Node Config:
    Node Pool Pod Network Option Details:
      Cni Type: OCI_VCN_IP_NATIVE
      Vcn Ip Native Pod Network Options:
        Nsg Names:
          pod
        Subnet Names:
          pod
      Nsg Names:
        worker
    Placement Configs:
      Availability Domain: BKrI:EU-FRANKFURT-1-AD-2
      Fault Domains:
        FAULT-DOMAIN-1
        FAULT-DOMAIN-2
        FAULT-DOMAIN-3
      Subnet Name:        worker
      Availability Domain: BKrI:EU-FRANKFURT-1-AD-3
      Fault Domains:
        FAULT-DOMAIN-1
        FAULT-DOMAIN-2
        FAULT-DOMAIN-3
      Subnet Name:        worker
      Availability Domain: BKrI:EU-FRANKFURT-1-AD-1
      Fault Domains:
        FAULT-DOMAIN-1
        FAULT-DOMAIN-2
        FAULT-DOMAIN-3
      Subnet Name:        worker
    Node Shape:          VM.Standard.E4.Flex
    Node Shape Config:
      Ocpus: 1
    Node Source Via Image:
      Boot Volume Size In G Bs: 50
      Image Id:           <ocid1.image.oc1.eu-frankfurt-1...>
      Provider ID:        <oci://ocid1.nodepool.oc1.eu-frankfurt-1...>
      Provider ID List:
        <ocid1.instance.oc1.eu-frankfurt-1...>
```



```

<ocid1.instance.oc1.eu-frankfurt-1...>
Version: v1.30.1
Status:
Conditions:
  Last Transition Time:      2024-08-13T09:32:37Z
  Status:                    True
  Type:                      NodePoolReady
Infrastructure Machine Kind: OCIMachinePoolMachine
Nodepool Lifecycle State:   UPDATING
Ready:                      true
Replicas:                   2
Events:
  Type      Reason          Age          From
  Message
  ----      -
  -
  Normal    NodePoolReady  58s (x2396 over 22h)  ocimanagedmachinepool-
  controller Node pool is in ready state

```

Figure 16. OCIManagedMachinePool CR after reconciliation test of CAPI on OCI

```

apiVersion: argoproj.io/v1alpha1
kind: Application
metadata:
  name: main-app
  namespace: argocd
  finalizers:
    - resources-finalizer.argocd.argoproj.io
spec:
  destination:
    namespace: default
    server: https://kubernetes.default.svc
  project: default
  source:
    path: sub-apps
    repoURL: <repoURL>
    targetRevision: HEAD
  syncPolicy:
    automated:
      prune: true

```

Figure 17. ArgoCD main app for the one button deployment

```

apiVersion: argoproj.io/v1alpha1

```



```

kind: Application
metadata:
  name: crossplane-core
  namespace: argocd
  annotations:
    argocd.argoproj.io/sync-wave: "1"
  finalizers:
    - resources-finalizer.argocd.argoproj.io
spec:
  project: default
  source:
    chart: crossplane
    repoURL: https://charts.crossplane.io/stable
    targetRevision: 1.16.0
    helm:
      releaseName: crossplane
  destination:
    server: "https://kubernetes.default.svc"
    namespace: crossplane-system
  syncPolicy:
    automated: {}
    syncOptions:
      - CreateNamespace=true

```

Figure 18. ArgoCD app for crossplane core deployment

```

apiVersion: argoproj.io/v1alpha1
kind: Application
metadata:
  name: crossplane-openstack-provider
  namespace: argocd
  annotations:
    argocd.argoproj.io/sync-wave: "2"
  finalizers:
    - resources-finalizer.argocd.argoproj.io
spec:
  destination:
    namespace: default
    server: https://kubernetes.default.svc
  project: default
  source:
    path: crossplane-openstack-provider
    repoURL: <repoURL>
    targetRevision: HEAD

```



```
syncPolicy:
  automated: {}
```

Figure 19. ArgoCD app for crossplane openstack provider

```
apiVersion: argoproj.io/v1alpha1
kind: Application
metadata:
  name: crossplane-argocd-provider
  namespace: argocd
  annotations:
    argocd.argoproj.io/sync-wave: "2"
  finalizers:
    - resources-finalizer.argocd.argoproj.io
spec:
  destination:
    namespace: default
    server: https://kubernetes.default.svc
  project: default
  source:
    path: crossplane-argocd-provider
    repoURL: <repoURL>
    targetRevision: HEAD
  syncPolicy:
    automated: {}
```

Figure 20. ArgoCD app for crossplane argocd provider

```
apiVersion: openstack.crossplane.io/v1beta1
kind: ProviderConfig
metadata:
  name: WHATEVER
spec:
  credentials:
    source: Secret
    secretRef:
      key: creds
      name: WHATEVER
      namespace: crossplane-clusters
```

Figure 21. Config base: provider-config.yaml

```
apiVersion: v1
```



```
kind: Secret
metadata:
  name: WHATEVER
  namespace: crossplane-clusters
type: Opaque
stringData:
  creds: WHATEVER
```

Figure 22. Config base: secret.yaml

```
apiVersion: containerinfra.openstack.crossplane.io/v1alpha1
kind: ClusterV1
metadata:
  annotations:
    crossplane.io/external-name: NAME
  name: NAME
spec:
  deletionPolicy: Orphan
  forProvider:
    name: NAME
    clusterTemplateId: kubernetes-1.25.3-3
    createTimeout: 60
    masterCount: 1
    masterFlavor: MASTER_FLAVOR
    nodeCount: COUNT
    flavor: FLAVOR
    keypair: shared-jeedy-key
    mergeLabels: true
    labels:
      admission_control_list:
        ExtendedResourceToleration, NamespaceLifecycle, LimitRanger, ServiceAccount, DefaultStorageClass, DefaultTolerationSeconds, MutatingAdmissionWebhook, ValidatingAdmissionWebhook, ResourceQuota, Priority
      autoscaler_tag: v1.22.0
      calico_ipv4pool: 10.100.0.0/16
      calico_ipv4pool_ipip: Always
      calico_tag: v3.24.5
      cephfs_csi_enabled: "false"
      cephfs_csi_version: cern-csi-1.0-3
      cern_chart_enabled: "true"
      cern_chart_version: 0.12.0
      cert_manager_api: "true"
      cgroup_driver: cgroupfs
      cloud_provider_enabled: "true"
```



```
cloud_provider_tag: v1.24.5
container_infra_prefix: <container_infra_prefix>
container_runtime: containerd
containerd_tarball_sha256: <containerd_tarball_sha256>
containerd_tarball_url: <containerd_tarball_url>
coredns_tag: 1.8.7
cvmfs_csi_enabled: "false"
cvmfs_csi_version: v2.0.0
eos_enabled: "false"
etcd_tag: v3.4.13
heapster_enabled: "false"
heat_container_agent_tag: train-stable-6
helm_client_tag: v2.16.6
ignition_version: 3.3.0
influx_grafana_dashboard_enabled: "false"
ingress_controller: ""
ip_family_policy: single_stack
kube_csi_enabled: "false"
kube_csi_version: cern-csi-1.0-2
kube_dashboard_enabled: "false"
kube_tag: v1.25.3-cern.0
kubepi_options: --feature-gates=CSIMigration=true
kubecontroller_options: --feature-gates=
kubenet_options: --feature-gates= --system-reserved=memory=500Mi --
resolv-conf=/run/systemd/resolve/resolv.conf
logging_installer: helm
manila_csi_enabled: "false"
manila_enabled: "false"
manila_version: v0.3.0
metrics_server_enabled: "true"
nginx_ingress_controller_tag: v1.0.4
nvidia_gpu_enabled: "false"
nvidia_gpu_tag: 35-5.16.13-200.fc35.x86_64-470.82.00
oidc_enabled: "false"
oidc_groups_claim: <oidc_groups_claim>
oidc_groups_prefix: <oidc_groups_prefix>
oidc_issuer_url: <oidc_issuer_url>
oidc_username_claim: <oidc_username_claim>
oidc_username_prefix: <oidc_username_prefix>
snapshot_controller_enabled: "false"
tiller_enabled: "true"
tiller_tag: v2.16.6
traefik_ingress_controller_tag: 2.5.4
use_podman: "true"
```



```

providerConfigRef:
  name: PROVIDER-CONFIG
writeConnectionSecretToRef:
  name: NAME
  namespace: crossplane-clusters

```

Figure 23. Cluster base: *clusterv1.yaml*

```

apiVersion: cluster.argocd.crossplane.io/v1alpha1
kind: Cluster
metadata:
  name: NAME
spec:
  forProvider:
    config:
      kubeconfigSecretRef:
        key: "attribute.kubeconfig.raw_config"
        name: NAME
        namespace: crossplane-clusters
    name: NAME
  providerConfigRef:
    name: argocd-provider

```

Figure 24. Cluster base: *cluster.yaml*

```

- op: replace
  path: /metadata/annotations/crossplane.io~1external-name
  value: {{cluster_name}}
- op: replace
  path: /metadata/name
  value: {{cluster_name}}
- op: replace
  path: /spec/forProvider/name
  value: {{cluster_name}}
{%if master_count != "1" %}
- op: replace
  path: /spec/forProvider/masterCount
  value: {{master_count}}
{% endif %}
- op: replace
  path: /spec/forProvider/masterFlavor
  value: {{master_flavor}}
- op: replace
  path: /spec/forProvider/nodeCount

```



```
  value: {{node_count}}
- op: replace
  path: /spec/forProvider/flavor
  value: {{flavor}}
{% for name, value in replaced_labels.items() %}
- op: replace
  path: /spec/forProvider/labels/{{name}}
  value: "{{value}}"
{% endfor %}
{% for name, value in added_labels.items() %}
- op: add
  path: /spec/forProvider/labels/{{name}}
  value: "{{value}}"
{% endfor %}
- op: replace
  path: /spec/providerConfigRef/name
  value: {{provider_config}}
- op: replace
  path: /spec/writeConnectionSecretToRef/name
  value: {{cluster_name}}
```

Figure 25. Overlay template for patch-clusterv1.yaml